

Assessing Heavy and Trace Metals in Key Fish and Shellfish Species of Bangladesh: Implications for Human Health Standard

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Abstract

Fish and shellfish are the prime and valuable protein sources for humans and aquatic animals. They play an essential role in supporting the livelihoods of rural households as well as contributing to the economy of Bangladesh through local and foreign currency earnings. This study focused on the heavy metal (HM) and trace element concentrations of seven commercially important fish and shellfish species collected from the four different fish markets in Chattogram City, Bangladesh, to assess potential risks to human health. Heavy metals of cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), and chromium (Cr), along with trace elements such as copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), nickel (Ni), and cobalt (Co), were measured in the muscle tissue of fishes, viz., Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), Bata (*Labeo bata*), Thai Pangas (*Pangasius hypophthalmus*), Loitta (*Harpodon nehereus*), Hilsha (*Tenualosa ilisha*), Poa (*Otolithoides pama*), and shellfish of Giant Freshwater Prawn (*Macrobrachium rosenbergii*). An atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used for the analysis following a standardized method. The trace metal concentrations in wet weight varied for copper (Cu): 1.12-7.52 mg/kg, zinc (Zn): 4.11-18.24 mg/kg, and manganese (Mn): 0.38-3.14 mg/kg. In contrast, the levels of lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), chromium (Cr), and cobalt (Co) were below detectable limits across all species tested. The current heavy and trace metal levels of this study were within the safety limits recommended by FAO, WHO, EU, and the Bangladesh Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, and Food (MAFF) for consumption. In essence, our study emphasizes the need for continued monitoring and regulation to protect public health.

keywords: Heavy metal; Trace element; Human health standard; Commercial fish; Shellfish; Bangladesh.